

REINFORCING TEACHERS` RESILIENCE STRATEGIES IN SOUTH AFRICAN SCHOOLS DURING AND AFTER THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract

At its height, the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant and lasting practical and psychological impact on the world, with over six hundred million **infections** and six and a half million **deaths** worldwide (www.worldometers, 2022). In South Africa, all governmental and non-governmental were affected, particularly education as teachers faced numerous hurdles attempting to maintain effective teaching and learning. Many alternative and innovative teaching methods were implemented, but without considering teaching staff capacity to cope. Changes, including the number of subjects taught and reduction in content and assessment, continue to impact schools as learners in lower grades suffer from the resulting content gap. Based on these challenges, the main question for this paper is: What were teachers` resilience strategies and how were these reinforced by the Department of Education? The study on which it is based employed a qualitative research design, with data collected through open-ended questionnaire distributed to 32 purposively sampled Life Sciences teachers in 25 schools in a rural district of Free State province. Only 10 usable instruments were received. From analysis, three themes emerged, namely, psychological effect, resilience strategies, and pedagogical support received and required. Results showed that teachers were overwhelmed by COVID-19 itself and by the content which had to be covered in spite of the lockdown and closure of schools. Findings indicated that in addition to material and guidelines received from education officials, various strategies were used by individual teachers relying on their mobile telephones and/or computers. Lastly, the content gap was identified from the cohort of learners whose subjects had to be trimmed and work coverage reduced. This now needs be filled, as the pandemic appears to be diminishing in impact, as teachers are still not coping with the extra workload, despite the material and guidelines received. Notable was the major role played by departmental officials in strengthening teacher resilience during the pandemic, however, acknowledging a need for its reinforcement, the paper recommends workshops to equip teachers with appropriate technological and pedagogical skills, such as computer application and online interaction. Additional workshops should be conducted in simplified methods to reduce workload.

Keywords: COVID-19, lockdown, resilience, pedagogical support.

1 INTRODUCTION

Restrictions on, or complete suspension of interaction between teachers and learners due to COVID-19 strained the relationship between teaching and learning. Some notes were sent to learners for continued study at home but not all could access them, whilst practical subjects and content in other subjects became a challenge. It was therefore difficult to decide on how to make assessment fair. Interaction time had been shortened and annual teaching plans were overloaded. As a result, the Minister of Basic Education deemed it necessary to review education policies and guidelines. Subject content had to be trimmed and a decision taken on which content to cut so the rest could fit in the remaining time. The process appeared helpful at the time but the consequences expose a content gap as the pandemic eased. Individual teachers had their own

ways of managing their subjects, however, it was necessary for them to receive assistance by reinforcing their strategies since they had been affected psychologically. The work scheduled over a year had been compressed, leading to extended hours of work but no decrease in expectations for outstanding competitive performance. Some teachers themselves contracted the virus, whilst during lockdown all continued to readjust their lifestyle and work tempo.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

COVID-19 became a crisis when workplaces had to find other means of continuing with their daily business to curb spread of the virus. Efforts such as e-learning enhancement were put in place to reschedule education processes (Vazquez, Verde, dal Mas, palemo, Mobianchi, Marescaux, Gallix, Dallenmagne, Perretta & Gimenez: 2020). The Minister of Education and management structures created simplified opportunities for academics, whilst responsibilities of managers were reviewed and distributed with clear lines of implementation. For instance, guidelines on how to teach and assess teaching and learning were distributed by the Department of Basic Education (Gaur, Majumder, Sa, Sarkar, Williams & Singh: 2020), whilst from the Department of Education teachers received abridged curriculum policy documents guiding simplified application for their survival. Technology resources became available through online platforms that enabled virtual discourse, notably *Zoom*.

As the pandemic eased, teachers were faced with pressure as learners had lost the incentive to work hard and attend regularly for the whole week at all the hours scheduled for teaching and learning. Teachers were expected to complete the syllabi scheduled for the year, coupled with the gap content caused by the two years of lockdown, in an inclusive and fair manner (Gaur et al.: 2020). Technology was seen a way of closing all the gaps speedily but not all teachers were competent in its use, hence the need to enhance utilisation of digital technology to reinforce teaching strategies (Sikhakhane, Govender & Maphalala: 2022). According to Baruah and Mohalik (2022), teacher development through techno-pedagogical skills should see effective integration of computer technology in the administration of teaching-learning and assessment activities. As much as technological application is an approach to transformation in the evolution of education it has been coupled with expensive gadgetry and data, compounding the challenges to low earning teachers and underdeveloped schools (Jorstad: 2009, Hirshman, 2016).

A study conducted in Japan by Matsushita and Yamamura (2022) found that extended hours of work and teachers being expected to accomplish the existing responsibilities of teaching can cause stress, fatigue and isolation. Similarly, in Germany, Kreuzfeld, Felsing & Seibt (2022) confirmed that long working hours have a negative impact on the wellbeing of some teachers and lead to emotional exhaustion. Long working hours weakens teachers' wellbeing (Jerrim, 2020), therefore, reinforcing their resilience strategies would reduce risks to health in the aftermath of the pandemic.

3 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Resilience that sustained teachers during the pandemic and kept them going during and post the pandemic is understood in this paper as being a coping mechanism during stressful working situations which develops new strategies and increased effort to solve a problem. It is linked to self-efficacy, which is a belief in one's ability to solve problems and handle stress (Kennedy, 2022).

4 METHODOLOGY

The study's qualitative methods included an open-ended questionnaire administered to a sample consisting of 32 purposively selected teachers of Life Sciences in the 25 schools in a rural district of Free State. It was emailed to all 25 schools and responses were emailed back, though only 10 usable tools were received. This suggests how overloaded teachers were, some not having time to complete the questionnaire in the given time. Below are the research questions which guided the study.

4.1 Research questions

What were teachers' resilience strategies during Covid-19 and after?

How were these reinforced by the Department of Education?

4.2 Findings and discussion

The collected data was analysed and themes emerging were psychological effect, pedagogical support and resilience strategies required.

4.2.1 Psychological effect

The data indicated that indeed teachers were psychologically affected during and after COVID 19. They experienced stress and required more time due to feelings of being slow in the processes of teaching and learning. Learner absenteeism was also indicated as a contributor to teacher stress since more time would be required.

4.2.2 Pedagogical support

About 20% of teachers used computer technology to record lessons which they shared with learners as videos. Virtual lessons were held, continuing from the years` of COVID-19 era and afterwards. The other 10% of teachers depended on mobile telephones as another method of interaction and sharing lessons to keep up with the scheduled content time. It was evident that teachers received significantly material and documents from the Department of Education officials, ranging from amended curriculum policies, developed lessons, recorded lessons and assessment activities.

4.2.3 Resilience strategy need

Data showed that resources such as mobile telephones and computers were used by teachers and learners to augment document material received from the officials. A further indication was a need of teacher reinforcement in computer application to enhancement of their teaching strategies (30%).

5 DISCUSSIONS

From the data responses it was evident that approaches put in place to assist teachers during the pandemic are continuing. More pedagogical strategies are needed to cope with the increased workload. Technological appliances are appropriate in resolving the problem, with more workshops to train and equip teachers with more advanced computer and online technology.

6 RECOMMENDATIONS

The Department of Education should take into cognisance that in addition to material being developed and distributed to teachers it is necessary to provide technological resources that are user friendly and account for time. Workshops should be conducted to train teachers on how to integrate technological resources, such as computers, into teaching, learning and assessment. Schools should also consider allowing learners access to computers for rapid communication and timesaving. Data should be made available in schools to assist both the teachers and the learners while integrating computer technology in the teaching and learning process.

7 CONCLUSION

The study unfolded through an open-ended questionnaire to provide a picture of the psychological effect, pedagogical support, and teachers` resilience strategies arising from experience of the COVID-19 pandemic. Deduced from the sampled schools, analysis indicated that support was received from the Department of Education, although it appeared inadequate. More needs to be carried out through provision of technological resources and online innovation, particularly innovative techno-digital utilization (Baruah & Mohalik, 2022), minimising extended hours of work and reduction in stress. The study confirms that reinforcing resilience strategies for teachers is necessary for their wellbeing. Training them how to use resources they have received and their integration in the classroom is necessary. It is acknowledged that teachers developed their own ways of dealing with the challenges of COVID-19 and its aftermath, however, enhancement is still necessary for their effective pedagogical practice.

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